

1D and 2D fractional-order Legendre wavelets for solving 1D and 2D fractional-order differential equations with proportional delay

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a numerical solution based on fractional-order Legendre wavelets for solving fractional-order differential equations with proportional delay. Operational matrix of fractional-order integration with the collocation points are utilized to reduce the solution of under study problem to a system of algebraic equations.

Keywords: Fractional partial differential equations; Fractional-order wavelets; Numerical method

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1 Introduction

Delay differential equations (DDE) have various applications in mathematical modeling, for example, physiological and pharmaceutical kinetics, chemical kinetics, the navigational control of ships and aircrafts, population dynamics, and infectious diseases. They arise when the rate of change of a time-dependent process in its mathematical modeling is not only determined by its present state but also by a certain past state. The pantograph equation is one of the most important kinds of DDEs, and plays an important role in explaining many different phenomena.

1.1 1D Fractional-order Legendre wavelets

The 1D fractional-order Legendre wavelets are defined on $[0, 1)$ as [1]

$$\psi_{n,m}^{\alpha}(t) = \begin{cases} ((2m+1)\alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} Fl_m^{\alpha}(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M-1$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$.

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1.2 2D fractional-order Legendre wavelets

The 2D fractional-order Legendre wavelets are defined on $[0, 1) \times [0, 1)$ as:

$$\psi_{n,m,n',m'}(x,t) = \begin{cases} ((2m+1)\alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}}((2m'+1)\alpha)^{\frac{1}{2}}2^{\frac{k+k'}{2}-1}Fl_m^\alpha(2^{k-1}x-\hat{n})Fl_{m'}^\alpha(2^{k'-1}t-\tilde{n}), \\ \quad \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq x < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{\tilde{n}}{2^{k'-1}} \leq t < \frac{\tilde{n}+1}{2^{k'-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{n} = n - 1$, $\tilde{n} = n' - 1$ and $\hat{m} = 2^{k-1}M$; $\tilde{m} = 2^{k'-1}M'$.

2 Operational matrix of fractional integral

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integration of the vector $\Psi(x, t)$ as:

$$I_x^q \Psi(x, t) = \wp(x, q) \Psi(x, t) = (\rho_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}}(x, q) \otimes I_{\tilde{m} \times \tilde{m}}) \Psi(x, t), \quad (3)$$

$$I_t^{q'} \Psi(x, t) = \wp'(t, q') \Psi(x, t) = (I_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}} \otimes \rho'_{\tilde{m} \times \tilde{m}}(t, q')) \Psi(x, t), \quad (4)$$

where I is identity matrix; $\rho(x, q)$ and $\rho'(t, q')$ are the fractional integration operational matrices of 1D fractional-order Legendre wavelets.

3 Problem statement and numerical method

One dimensional case: Consider fractional differential equations with pantograph delay as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^q z(x)}{\partial x^q} = b(x)z(x) + \sum_{r=1}^{\ell} a_r(x)z(\xi_r x) & 0 \leq x < 1, 0 < q \leq 1, \\ z(0) = \lambda_0. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

For solving this problem, we approximate functions $\frac{\partial^q z(x)}{\partial x^q}$, $z(x)$ and $z(\xi_r x)$ as:

$$\frac{\partial^q z(x)}{\partial x^q} \simeq C^T \Psi(x),$$

$$z(x) \simeq C^T \rho(x, q) \Psi(x) + \lambda_0,$$

$$z(\xi_r x) \simeq C^T \rho(\xi_r x, q) \Psi(\xi_r x) + \lambda_0.$$

Replacing above relations in Eq. (5) and collocating this equation at the zeros of shifted Legendre polynomials.

Two-dimensional case: Consider fractional partial differential equations with proportional delay as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^q z(x,t)}{\partial x^q} = F(x, t, z(a_0 x, b_0 t), \frac{\partial^\gamma z(a_1 x, b_1 t)}{\partial x^\gamma}, \frac{\partial^{q'} z(a_2 x, b_2 t)}{\partial t^{q'}}), & 0 \leq x, t < 1, \\ z(x, 0) = f_0(x), & z(0, t) = g_0(t), & z(1, t) = g_1(t), \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

For solving this problem, we approximate following functions as:

$$\frac{\partial^q z(x, t)}{\partial x^q} \simeq C^T \wp'(t, q') \Psi(x, t) + \frac{\partial^q f_0(x)}{\partial x^q}. \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{q'} z(a_2x, b_2t)}{\partial t^{q'}} &\simeq C^T \wp(a_2x, q) \Psi(a_2x, b_2t) - (a_2x)(C^T \wp(1, q) \Psi(1, b_2t)) \\ &+ (1 - (a_2x)) \frac{\partial^{q'} g_0(b_2t)}{\partial t^{q'}} + (a_2x) \frac{\partial^{q'} g_1(b_2t)}{\partial t^{q'}}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} z(a_0x, b_0t) &\simeq C^T \wp'(b_0t, q') \wp(a_0x, q) \Psi(a_0x, b_0t) \\ &- (a_0x)(C^T \wp'(b_0t, q') \wp(1, q) \Psi(1, b_0t)) + \Delta(a_0x, b_0t), \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^\gamma z(a_1x, b_1t)}{\partial x^\gamma} &\simeq C^T \wp'(b_1t, q') \wp(a_1x, q - \gamma) \Psi(a_1x, b_1t) \\ &- \frac{(a_1x)^{1-\gamma}}{\Gamma(2 - \gamma)} (C^T \wp'(b_1t, q') \wp(1, q) \Psi(1, b_1t)) + \frac{\partial^\gamma \Delta(a_1x, b_1t)}{\partial x^\gamma}. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Replacing Eqs. (7) - (10) in Eq. (6) and collocating this equation at the zeros of shifted Legendre polynomials.

4 Computational results

In this section, we consider two examples to demonstrate the performance and accuracy of the present method.

Example 1. Consider the fractional multi-pantograph differential equation [2]

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^q z(x)}{\partial x^q} = -\frac{5}{6}z(x) + 4z(\frac{1}{2}x) + 9z(\frac{1}{3}x) + x^2 - 1, & 0 \leq x < 1, 0 < q \leq 1, \\ z(0) = 1. \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

The exact solution, when $q = 1$ is $z(x) = 1 + \frac{67}{6}x + \frac{1675}{72}x^2 + \frac{12157}{1296}x^3$.

Example 2. Consider time-fractional order, generalized Burgers equation with proportional delay

Figure 1: Approximate solutions of $z(x)$ with $q = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9$ and $\alpha = q, k = 2, M = 4$ for Example 1.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^{q'} z(x,t)}{\partial t^{q'}} = \frac{\partial^2 z(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + z(\frac{x}{2}, \frac{t}{2}) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} u(x, \frac{t}{2}) + \frac{1}{2}u(x, t), & 0 \leq x, t < 1, 0 < q' \leq 1, \\ z(x, 0) = x, & z(0, t) = 0, & z(1, t) = e^t, \end{cases} \tag{12}$$

The exact solution, when $q' = 1$ is $z(x, t) = xe^t$.

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Table 1: Comparison of absolute error for $k = k' = 2, M = M' = 2, \alpha = \frac{1}{2}, 1$ for Example 2.

x	t	[3]	Our method	
			$\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$	$\alpha = 1$
0.25	0.25	2.122401×10^{-6}	0	0
	0.50	7.094268×10^{-5}	0	0
	0.75	5.634807×10^{-4}	0	0
0.5	0.25	4.244802×10^{-6}	0	0
	0.50	1.418854×10^{-4}	0	0
	0.75	1.126961×10^{-3}	0	0
0.75	0.25	6.369688×10^{-6}	0	0
	0.50	2.128250×10^{-4}	0	0
	0.75	1.690020×10^{-3}	0	0

Figure 2: Approximate solutions of with $q' = 0.8, 0.9, 1$ and $\alpha = q'$ for Example 2.

References

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